

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE COORDINATION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND THE USE OF TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *The digital era is a creator of learning modern English language from the youngest population to the three cycles of the higher education system. Internet connections and technological innovations transformed into modern tools such as computers, tablets, smartphones, smartwatches upgraded with modern platforms such as Moodle, Blackboard, etc., are not only a necessity but also an obligation of every individual and institution for advanced and modern learning of English Language.*

Keywords: *digital technologies, English language, teaching, Moodle, video clips, movies.*

INTRODUCTION

Some of the tools that can be used in the EFL classroom are: digital storytelling, comics, eBooks, videos, images, online speaking avatars and interactive whiteboards that can be accessed via the internet. The advancement of technology is now evident with studies showing about 90% of pupils having access to a mobile device or computer whether at home, school or work. It is therefore not surprising that teaching methods have also evolved towards embracing technology. The new teaching era has been marked with examples of modern teaching such as blended learning, on-line open-source platforms, as well as virtual teaching classrooms that are being endorsed by major education experts. These new teaching methods integrate technology in English language teaching to facilitate teachers, to improve the engagement of the pupil and for everyone involved produce a comprehensive, structured environment for learning. It is therefore evident that educational institutions require transitioning to a more technologically oriented classroom.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The application of new technologies greatly increases the creativity of teachers in the application of new methods in the study of the English language, and thus, largely, takes the teacher's responsibility [2]. The application of new technologies not only raises the level and quality of English language learning that is functionally related to the modernity offered by new tools and modern software in the presentation of the material, but the new technologies cause a sense of additional activity and mobilisation of each pupil, listening to the subject material that is presented in the classroom. These take on the role of an additional motivator and stimulator for not only pupils as listeners, but also for teachers who see the challenge in adopting modern tools, which include computers, tablets, smartphones, smartwatches, interactive boards, e-learning platforms (Moodle, Blackboard, and Google Classroom), etc (Figure 1).

Figure. 1. Illustration of modern tools used in English language teaching

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With the application of these modern tools, teachers have the opportunity to apply and implement learning methodologies that have proved to be very successful in studying English. Methodologically, this further means that teachers provide a different level of training among the listeners, with full efficiency in the presentation of the material and the exercises [7].

New technology edged up over the years but not everything remained the same. This may be result of the growing concerns over security and the wearing out of some innovations. Those that have stood the test of time possess a solid teaching practice.

Blended learning- here trend is reflected by course material and resources of teachers as they combine technology with the more comprehended traditional mode of teaching. Blended learning is a more preferred classroom interaction model due to fact that it accommodates the learning style of each pupil to reach the highest level of absorbance.

Mobile learning. - it is evident that mobile apps provide more access to online resources. For example, Oxford University Press uses Essential English to give pupils and teachers free resources that consist of flashcards, lesson plans, phrasebooks, etc.

Gamification were learning occurs through the use of gaming apps and software. Interactive games help language skills to be used to collaborate, negotiate, and create friendships [8].

Embodied learning is not strictly based on remembering, it also entails the use of the body and mind, exploring, discussing and collaborating. For instance, Doodle Town course by Macmillan Education involves hands-on activities, visual and audio to inspire and stimulate the learner thus getting them to be inquisitive, to create and draw. Learning and teaching management platforms - such as Edmodo provide learners with online access to handouts, submit homework, and continue with classroom discussions. Currently, online platforms are being additionally used to communicate with stakeholders and parents, assist in the management of materials and lesson plans, and provide a better curriculum overview for the teachers and the administrative staff.

CONCLUSION

The application of new technologies in ELT in today's conditions is inescapable to maintain the trend of systematic learning of modern English at all levels of education [9]. The Computers, Internet, modern platforms, smartphones and watches are tools that pave

the essential way of using modern tools for learning English language fully and quickly. The application of modern technologies at the schools shows a positive trend, which is directly reflected in the percentage of those technologies and their application of the teaching staff. The most commonly used platform is Moodle with 40%, while Google Classroom is used with 10% (but with great progress in the past period). Filmed stories and videos are used regularly by teachers in learning English with 55%, while they are occasionally used in 45% of cases.

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